

SECTION OF CHEMICAL SCIENCES

SUPRAMOLECULAR CONSTRUCTS IN LIDOCAINE COMPLEXES WITH ZINC AND COPPER TETRACHLORIDES

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Abstract

The action of local anesthetics is determined by the ability of their molecules to form supramolecular structures through intermolecular hydrogen bonds. Using X-ray crystallography data, supramolecular structures in crystals of the typical amide anesthetics lidocaine, its salt, and complexes with zinc and copper tetrachlorides are examined. It has been shown that in lidocaine, hydrogen bonds form ring-shaped zero-dimensional supramolecular constructs $R_1^1(5)$ and one-dimensional infinite chains; in lidocaine hydrochloride monohydrate, rings $R_4^4(18)$ and one-dimensional ribbons are formed, while lidocaine complexes are characterized by the formation of zero-dimensional supramolecular rings of the $R_1^1(5)$ and $R_2^2(10)$ types, which are part of one-dimensional chains and large rings ($R_{20}^{20}(74)$ and $R_{14}^{14}(58)$ for zinc and copper, respectively) that form two-dimensional supramolecular constructs of various types of honeycombs.

Keywords: lidocaine, X-ray analysis, hydrogen bonds, supramolecular constructs.

Introduction. It is believed that local anesthetics work by reversibly binding to and blocking voltage-gated sodium channels in nerve cell membranes [1]. Local anesthetics are water-soluble salts of lipid-soluble alkaloids, their molecular structure consists of a lipophilic aromatic group, an intermediate link that allows local anesthetics to be classified into esters (cocaine, chloroprocaine, prilocaine) and amides (lidocaine, mepivacaine, bupivacaine), and a hydrophilic amino group. The step-by-step mechanism of action of local anesthetics [1,2] involves the stages of (i) penetration, when the uncharged (lipophilic) anesthetic molecule diffuses through the neuronal membrane, (ii) ionization, as a result of which some of the uncharged molecules acquire a positive charge, and (iii) sodium channel blockade, when charged anesthetic molecules bind to and block the open voltage-gated sodium channel located in domain IV, loop S6 [3], thereby preventing the influx of sodium ions (Na^+) needed to depolarize the nerve cell membrane, which stops the propagation of nerve impulses, and the person loses sensation in that area. The importance of hydrogen bond formation by the anesthetic molecule in the mechanism of action, particularly at the binding stage, was noted more than half a century ago [4]. It is generally accepted that general anesthetics act by perturbing intermolecular associations without breaking or forming covalent bonds [5]. For example, general anesthetics can cause a restructuring of the "hydrogen belts" of cell membranes, disrupting hydrogen bonds between lipids and proteins [6], while local anesthetics act as hydrogen bond donors, forming a complex with an acceptor group on the neuronal membrane [7]. Protonation of the nitrogen atom of the amino group during the ionization stage makes this atom a donor; in amide local anesthetics, the corresponding nitrogen atom is also a donor.

At the same time, the ability of a molecule to form intermolecular hydrogen bonds makes it possible to

form supramolecular constructs – molecular assemblies held together by non-covalent bonds and forming larger structures through self-assembly [8]. The geometry and strength of hydrogen bonds allow molecules to form large and well-defined structures such as supramolecular polymers [9], chiral supramolecular assemblies [10,11], stimuli-responsive modules [12], multiple hydrogen bond assisted interpenetrating polymer networks [13], organic frameworks [14,15], supramolecular nanoadhesives [16], energy dissipators [17], etc. Supramolecular assemblies are used in the creation of biomedical materials, particularly in the design of drugs for myotonic dystrophy, molecular assembly for advanced drug delivery, tissue engineering, and self-assembly complexes as gene delivery vectors for gene transfection [18].

The aim of this research was to identify the types of supramolecular constructs in the typical amide local anesthetic lidocaine (2-(diethylamino)-*N*-(2,6-dimethylphenyl)acetamide, $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{22}\text{ON}_2$, Lid) and its compounds using graph-set analysis, for which the geometric and energetic characteristics of hydrogen bonds are irrelevant. In this approach [19], a graph set is specified using the pattern designator $G_d^a(r)$ (with degree (r), and the number of donors (d) and acceptors (a)), having four different assignments: (i) S – intramolecular hydrogen bond; (ii) $C_d^a(r)$ – infinite hydrogen-bonded intermolecular chains; (iii) $R_d^a(r)$ – rings; (iv) $D_d^a(r)$ – noncyclic dimers and other finite hydrogen-bonded sets. S bonds, R rings and D dimers are considered zero-dimensional supramolecular constructs (motifs), and C chains are considered one-dimensional supramolecular constructs.

In the analysis conducted, we used both literature data on the crystal structure of lidocaine [20-23] and lidocaine hydrochloride monohydrate [24], and our

own data on the structure of bis(lidocaine) tetrachloridozincate(II) [25] and bis(lidocaine) tetrachloridocuprate(II) [26].

Experimental

Copper(II) and zinc(II) complexes with lidocaine were prepared in weakly acidic (pH = 5-6) aqueous-methanol solutions with a molar ratio of metal chloride to lidocaine hydrochloride monohydrate of 1:2, details are described in [25] and [26], respectively.

The single crystal X-ray diffraction measurements were carried out with an Oxford Diffraction XCALIBUR E CCD diffractometer equipped with graphite-monochromated MoK α radiation ($\mu = 1.100 \text{ mm}^{-1}$, $F_{000} = 1422$, $\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$, temperature

100(2)K); the data collection, cell refinement and data reduction were carried out with the CrysAlis^{PRO} package of Rigaku Oxford Diffraction (version 1.171.38.46, 2015); the structure was solved by direct methods and refined against F^2 with full-matrix least-squares using the software complex SHELXL-2014, important details of data collection, cell refinement and data reduction are given in Table 1. Additional calculations of interatomic distances and angles in hydrogen bonds not detected by the SHELXL software were performed using Xseed software.

Table 1.

Crystal data and details of data collection for (LidH)₂[CuCl₄].

Data	(LidH) ₂ [ZnCl ₄]	(LidH) ₂ [CuCl ₄]
Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre reference file	1859311	2103365
Space group	<i>P</i> ₂ / <i>c</i> (No. 14)	<i>P</i> ₂ / <i>c</i> (No. 14)
a (Å)	8.8921(2)	15.7831(2)
b (Å)	19.2650(3)	24.2992(2)
c (Å)	19.3211(3)	17.8748(2)
β (°)	95.026(2)	104.874(1)
V (Å ³)	3297.1(1)	6625.58(13)
Z	4	8
Crystal size (mm)	0.47 × 0.36 × 0.35	0.44 × 0.28 × 0.21
2 Θ (°)	5 – 65.2	5 – 65.4
Reflections collected	39836	145922
Independent reflections	11211 ($R_{\text{int}} = 0.034$)	23126 ($R_{\text{int}} = 0.032$)
Final GOF	1.001	1.001
$R[F^2 > 2\sigma(F^2)]$	0.0336	0.031
wR_2	0.0783	0.078
Data, restraints, parameters	9057, 0, 376	18584, 0, 751
$ \Delta\rho _{\text{max}}$ (eÅ ⁻³)	0.49(7)	0.55(6)

Results and Discussion

Lidocaine. The lidocaine molecule consists of an aromatic ring with two methyl substituents in ortho positions to the flexible C₁–N₁₁H–C₁₂(=O)–C₁₃H₂–N₁₄(CH₂CH₃)₂ chain carrying donors and acceptors; in the crystalline state, rotation around the C₁–N₁₁, N₁₁–C₁₂, C₁₂–C₁₃ and C₁₃–N₁₄ bonds is inhibited and various conformations can be realized, determining the possibility of forming intramolecular and intermolecular hydrogen bonds of various types.

The first researchers of the structure of lidocaine, Neville and Cook, based on the infrared spectroscopy data, came to the conclusion that the amide group NH–C(=O) has a *cis*-conformation, which does not allow the formation of intramolecular hydrogen bonds, but promotes the formation of two bonds intramolecular hydrogen N–H \cdots O bonds [20], as shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Lidocaine in the *cis* amide configuration according to Neville and Cook [20].

In terms of graph-set analysis, this arrangement of molecules means that lidocaine forms zero-dimensional supramolecular construct $R_2^2(8)$, which is very

common in crystalline organic compounds [27] – six types of $R_2^2(8)$ dimers are known, including the one

possible in lidocaine, where the donors are amide nitrogen atoms and the acceptors are carbonyl oxygen atoms.

However, Chupp [21], using NMR data, considered the *trans*-configuration of the amide with formation of intramolecular $N_{11}-H\cdots N_{14}$ hydrogen bond

Fig. 2. Lidocaine in the *trans* amide configuration according to Chupp [21].

According to the more accurate low temperature (173 K) data of Bambagiotti-Alberti et al. (CCDC 636633, [23]), lidocaine crystallizes in monoclinic space group $P2_1/c$, with $a = 12.9590(3)$ Å, $b = 13.8003(3)$ Å, $c = 18.8288(5)$ Å, $\beta = 122.340(3)^\circ$, $Z=8$, and alternating crystallographically different molecules of lidocaine A and B. The conformations of the independent A and B molecules are very similar, in both molecules, the planar amide group is in the *trans* configuration (dihedral angle $H-N_{11}-C_{12}=O$ is $\sim 3^\circ$), nitrogen atoms N_{11} and N_{14} adopt a *synperiplanar* conformation, and the intramolecular hydrogen bond $N_{11}-H\cdots N_{14}$ ($N_{11}\cdots N_{14}$ distances of 2.678(2) and 2.695(2) Å, and $N_{11}-H\cdots N_{14}$ angles of 112.9(16) and 109.7(15) $^\circ$, for A and B molecules, respectively) not only stabilizes the

conformation relative to the $C_{12}-C_{13}$ bond, but also forms a five-atom $H-N_{11}-C_{12}-C_{13}-N_{14}$ ring with one donor (N_{11}) and one acceptor (N_{14}), corresponding to the zero-dimensional supramolecular construct $R_1^1(5)$.

The amide protons also participate in the intermolecular $N_{11}-H\cdots O_{12}$ bond ($N_{11}\cdots O_{12}$ distances of 2.8746(17) and 2.8952(18) Å, and $N_{11}-H\cdots O_{12}$ angle of 140.9(18) and 109.7(15) $^\circ$, for A and B molecules, respectively), and adjacent molecules are combined into chains $(-R_1^1(5)=O-)_n$ parallel to the crystallographic c axis, as shown in Figure 3. Thus, the one-dimensional supramolecular construct of lidocaine is the $C_1^2(6)$ chain, constructs of higher dimensions (2D, 3D) are not formed.

Fig. 3. Part of one hydrogen-bonded chain, viewed along b , according to Hanson and Banner [22].

Lidocaine hydrochloride monohydrate. Lidocaine base ($C_{14}H_{22}ON_2$, Lid) is poorly soluble in water and is usually used as the crystalline hydrate-forming hydrochloric acid salt $Lid\cdot HCl\cdot H_2O$. According to Hanson and Röhrh [25], in lidocaine hydrochloride monohydrate, a proton is transferred from the hydrochloride to the nitrogen atom of the amino group N_{14} to form the $LidH^+$ cation; the predominant crystal structure is fully hydrogen-bonded, utilizing all potential donor and ac-

ceptor groups, including the amino, amido, and carbonyl groups of lidocaine, as well as a water molecule and a chloride anion.

Neighboring cations $LidH^+$ are linked by water molecules H_2O through intermolecular hydrogen bonds $N_{11}-H\cdots O_{water}-H\cdots O-C_{12}$ into endless chains parallel to b crystallographic axis, and adjacent chains are held together by chloride ions Cl^- , each of which accepts an aqueous proton from one chain and an amino proton from the other with formation of a hydrogen-bonded double chain, as shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 4. Part of a hydrogen-bonded double chain in $\text{LidHCl}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ viewed along a , according to Hanson and Röhrl [24].

Figure 4 clearly shows the formation of a ring of 18 atoms $-\text{N}_{11}-\text{H}\cdots\text{O}-\text{H}\cdots\text{Cl}^--\text{H}-\text{N}_{14}-\text{C}_{13}-\text{C}_{12}=\text{O}'\cdots\text{H}-\text{O}-\text{H}\cdots\text{Cl}^--\text{H}-\text{N}_{14}-\text{C}_{13}-\text{C}_{12}-$, in which the nitrogen atoms N_{11} , N_{11}' , and N_{14} are donors, the chloride anions are acceptors, and two water molecules are donors and acceptors. Thus, the hydrogen bonds in lidocaine hydrochloride monohydrate form a $\text{R}_4^4(18)$ ring, which is translated along the b -axis, forming a one-dimensional supramolecular ribbon. These ribbons, or “double chains” in the terminology of Hanson and Röhrl, are not joined to their neighbors by any forces stronger than van der Waals.

Lidocaine complexes. The coordination compounds under consideration are charge-transfer complexes in which the coordination of the transition metal ion Me^{2+} ($\text{Me} = \text{Zn}, \text{Cu}$, etc.) with four chlorine anions forms a slightly distorted tetrahedral anion $[\text{MeCl}_4]^{2-}$, and two protonated LidH^+ cations remain in the outer

coordination sphere. In both compounds ($(\text{LidH})_2[\text{ZnCl}_4]$ and $(\text{LidH})_2[\text{CuCl}_4]$) the aromatic ring and the oxygen atom adopt a *synperiplanar* (C) conformation with respect to the carboxamide $\text{N}_{11}-\text{C}_{12}$ bond, while the amido N_{11} and amino N_{14} nitrogen atoms adopt a staggered *antiperiplanar* (T) conformation, which excludes the formation of an intramolecular hydrogen bond $\text{N}_{11}-\text{H}\cdots\text{N}_{14}$. Despite the fact that the torsion angle $\theta(\text{O}_{12}, \text{C}_{12}, \text{C}_{13}, \text{N}_{14})$ in some cases exceeds the limit determining the C conformation ($\pm 30^\circ$), calculations show the possibility of the formation of an intramolecular hydrogen bond $\text{N}_{14}-\text{H}\cdots\text{O}_{12}$. In the formation of intermolecular hydrogen bonds, the acceptors are chlorine and oxygen atoms.

Bis(lidocaine) tetrachloridozincate(II). The geometric parameters of intra- and intermolecular hydrogen bonds in $(\text{LidH})_2[\text{ZnCl}_4]$ are given in Table 2.

Table 2.

Geometry of hydrogen bonds generated by the SHELXL software and calculated with Xseed (*italic*)

D-H...A	D-H (Å)	H...A (Å)	D...A (Å)	D-H...A (°)
$\text{N}_{114}-\text{H}_{114}\cdots\text{O}_{112}$	0.885(18)	2.071(18)	2.6424(16)	121.4(15)
<i>$\text{N}_{214}-\text{H}_{214}\cdots\text{O}_{212}$</i>	<i>0.844</i>	<i>2.496</i>	<i>2.828</i>	<i>104.5</i>
$\text{N}_{211}-\text{H}_{211}\cdots\text{Cl}_1$	0.836(19)	2.415(18)	3.2349(12)	166.8(17)
$\text{N}_{111}-\text{H}_{111}\cdots\text{Cl}_3$	0.83(2)	2.50(2)	3.3124(13)	169.1(18)
<i>$\text{N}_{114}^{\text{iv}}-\text{H}_{114}^{\text{iv}}\cdots\text{Cl}_4$</i>	<i>0.885</i>	<i>2.508</i>	<i>3.184</i>	<i>133.69</i>
$\text{N}_{114}-\text{H}_{114}\cdots\text{Cl}_4^{\text{i}}$	0.885(18)	2.508(19)	3.1842(13)	133.7(15)
$\text{N}_{214}-\text{H}_{214}\cdots\text{O}_{212}^{\text{iii}}$	0.844(17)	1.998(18)	2.7511(15)	148.1(16)
<i>$\text{N}_{214}^{\text{iii}}-\text{H}_{214}^{\text{iii}}\cdots\text{O}_{212}$</i>	<i>0.844</i>	<i>1.998</i>	<i>2.751</i>	<i>148.07</i>

Symmetry codes: (i) $-x+1, y-1/2, -z+1/2$; (iii) $-x, -y+1, -z+1$; (iv) $-x+1, y+1/2, -z+1/2$.

The amine nitrogen atom N_{114} of cation 1 participates in a bifurcation hydrogen bond – on the one hand, an intramolecular bond with the oxygen atom O_{112} with the formation of the $\text{R}_1^1(5)$ ring (see Figure 5), as

well as an intermolecular bond with the chlorine atom Cl_4^{i} of the neighboring complex, determined by the symmetry operation (i). The amine nitrogen atom H_{214} of cation 2 also participates in the bifurcation hydrogen

bond, but with the formation of the $R_2^2(10)$ ring shown in Figure 6.

Fig. 5. Ring $R_1^1(5)$ in the $(LidH)_2[ZnCl_4]$ complex shown in Cartesian coordinates.

Fig. 6. Ring $R_2^2(10)$ in the $(LidH)_2[ZnCl_4]$ complex shown in Cartesian coordinates.

The $R_1^1(5)$ and $R_2^2(10)$ rings form large $R_{20}^{20}(74)$ rings, each containing six zinc atoms, four $R_1^1(5)$ rings and two $R_2^2(10)$ rings (see Figure 7).

Fig. 4. Unit cell of $(LidH)_2[ZnCl_4]$ viewed along $[100]$ and showing $R_{20}^{20}(74)$ rings (for simplicity, methyl groups at the aromatic rings, ethyl groups at the amino group and hydrogen atoms not involved in formation of hydrogen bonds are not shown).

The hexagon formed by the zinc atoms of the supramolecular ring $R_{20}^{20}(74)$ has two sides of 13.954 Å in length (the zinc atoms are connected via the rings $R_2^2(10)$) and four sides of 9.956 Å in length (the zinc atoms are connected via the rings $R_1^1(5)$); the four zinc atoms (Zn , Zn^{110} , Zn^i and $Zn^{1/20}$) lie in one plane, forming a dihedral angle of 34.25° with the plane XY, and 55.75° with the plane YZ. The Zn^{iv} and Zn^{100} zinc atoms are in a zigzag or trans conformation, the distance between them is 13.923 Å, and they are 3.2 Å away from

the plane of the four zinc atoms. Formally, the $R_{20}^{20}(74)$ rings are zero-dimensional supramolecular constructs, and their arrangement into honeycomb-type spatial structures, forms two-dimensional supramolecular constructs.

Bis(lidocaine) tetrachloridocuprate(II). Unlike the zinc complex, $(LidH)_2[CuCl_4]$ contains two crystallographically distinct $[CuCl_4]^{2-}$ anions and four $LidH^+$ cations; the geometric parameters of hydrogen bonds in copper complex are given in Table 3.

Geometry of intramolecular, cation-anion and intermolecular hydrogen bonds according to SHELXL data and calculation results (*italic*).

D—H···A	D—H (Å)	H···A (Å)	D···A (Å)	D—H···A (°)
N111—H111···Cl11	0.845(16)	2.998(16)	3.4458(10)	115.4(12)
N211—H211···Cl11	0.798(18)	2.420(18)	3.2111(10)	171.2(16)
N311—H311···Cl22	0.856(16)	2.378(16)	3.2273(10)	171.8(14)
N411—H411···Cl22	0.840(17)	2.369(17)	3.2071(10)	175.2(15)
N414—H414···Cl11	0.881(17)	2.526(17)	3.2124(10)	135.3(14)
<i>N114—H114···O112</i>	<i>0.872(16)</i>	<i>2.261(18)</i>	<i>2.6397(15)</i>	
N214—H214···O212	0.872(17)	2.104(17)	2.6703(13)	106.09(15)
N314—H314···O312	0.882(16)	2.225(16)	2.7321(13)	122.1(14)
N414—H414···O412	0.881(17)	2.117(16)	2.6727(12)	116.2(12)
				120.3(14)
N114—H114···O112 ⁱ	0.872(16)	2.019(16)	2.8776(12)	167.8(15)
N214—H214···Cl22 ⁱⁱⁱ	0.872(17)	2.538(18)	3.2167(10)	135.4(14)
N314—H314···O312 ^v	0.882(16)	2.051(16)	2.8533(12)	150.8(14)
<i>N214ⁱⁱ—H214ⁱⁱ···Cl22^{iv}</i>	<i>0.8724(20)</i>	<i>3.52(2)</i>	<i>3.41(2)</i>	<i>89.9(2)</i>
<i>N214^{iv}—H214^{iv}···Cl22</i>	<i>0.8720(17)</i>	<i>2.5363(18)</i>	<i>3.2161(12)</i>	<i>135.4(15)</i>

Symmetry codes:

(i) $-x+1, -y, -z$; (ii) $-x+2, y-1/2, z+1/2$; (iii) $x-1, y, z$; (iv) $x+1, y, z$; (v) $-x+2, -y+1, -z$.

For all four cations, intramolecular hydrogen bonds of the type $H_{14}-H\cdots O_{12}$ are realized; for cations **2** and **4**, this leads to the formation of $R_1^1(5)$ rings (see Figure 5), and for cations **1** and **3**, intermolecular hydrogen bonds are additionally realized with the formation of $R_2^2(10)$ rings, shown in Figures 6 and 7.

The overall picture of the hydrogen bonds linking copper atoms in the complex, the unit cell and beyond is shown in Figure 8. Zero-dimensional constructs

$R_1^1(5)$ and $R_2^2(10)$ are part of the chains between copper atoms:

$\cdots Cu-Cl\cdots R_1^1(5)-NH\cdots Cl-Cu\cdots$, and

$\cdots Cu-Cl\cdots HN-R_2^2(10)\cdots Cl-Cu\cdots$.

The chains form a large ring $R_{14}^{14}(58)$ containing six chlorine atoms bonded to six different copper atoms, six donor NH groups, four $R_1^1(5)$ rings and two $R_2^2(10)$ rings, shown schematically in Figure 9.

Fig. 5. Rings $R_1^1(5)$ formed in cations **2** and **4** of the $(Li_dH)_2[CuCl_4]$ complex, shown in Cartesian coordinates.

Fig. 6. Ring $R_2^2(10)$ formed by adjacent cations 1 of the $(LidH)_2[CuCl_4]$ complex, shown in Cartesian coordinates.

Fig. 7. Ring $R_2^2(10)$ formed by adjacent cations 3 of the $(LidH)_2[CuCl_4]$ complex, shown in Cartesian coordinates.

Fig. 8. Pattern of intermolecular hydrogen bonds of the $(LidH)_2[CuCl_4]$ complex.

Fig. 9. Diagram of the $R_{14}^{14}(58)$ ring in the crystal structure of the $(LidH)_2[CuCl_4]$ complex.

Unlike the zinc complex, the large ring of the copper complex $R_{14}^{14}(58)$ does not include transition metal atoms; chlorine atoms are located at the vertices of the resulting hexagon; the distance between chlorine atoms linked through the $R_1^1(5)$ construct is 8.286 Å, and the

distance between chlorine atoms linked through the $R_2^2(10)$ construct is 12.01 Å. The scheme of formation of two-dimensional supramolecular constructs in zinc and copper complexes is shown in Figure 10.

Fig. 10. Scheme of two-dimensional supramolecular constructs in the $(LidH)_2[ZnCl_4]$ and $(LidH)_2[CuCl_4]$ complex.

Conclusions

Lidocaine is characterized by the formation of a zero-dimensional ring construct $R_1^1(5)$ due to the intramolecular hydrogen bond $N_{14}H \cdots O_{12}$. There is reason to believe that $R_1^1(5)$ rings are formed in all lidocaine compounds. In lidocaine, the $R_1^1(5)$ rings are part of infinite one-dimensional chains. In lidocaine hydrochloride monohydrate, the $R_1^1(5)$ rings are part of larger $R_4^4(18)$ rings that form infinite one-dimensional ribbons; two-dimensional supramolecular constructs are not formed in lidocaine and its hydrochloride monohydrate.

The coordination compounds under consideration, which are charge-transfer complexes, contain at least two crystallographically different lidocaine cations $LidH^+$, in one of which the $R_1^1(5)$ ring is retained without participating in intermolecular interactions, while

in the other, due to intermolecular hydrogen bonds, it forms a zero-dimensional dimer $R_2^2(10)$, the presence of which is also noted in the supramolecular structure of bis(lidocaine) tetrathiocyanatocobaltate(II) monohydrate [28].

The zero-dimensional supramolecular rings of the $R_1^1(5)$ and $R_2^2(10)$ types form large rings – $R_{20}^{20}(74)$ in bis(lidocaine) tetrachloridozincate(II), which includes six zinc atoms, and $R_{14}^{14}(58)$ in bis(lidocaine) tetrachloridocuprate(II), which does not include copper atoms but does include six chlorine atoms.

The combination of large rings into honeycomb-type spatial structures that differ for $R_{20}^{20}(74)$ and $R_{14}^{14}(58)$ forms two-dimensional supramolecular constructs.

For both studied coordination compounds, using the SHELXL and Xseed software, non-classical hydrogen bonds of the C–H···O, C–H···N and C–H···Cl types were identified, which ensure the formation of three-dimensional supramolecular constructs, but this is the topic of our subsequent studies and reports, as well as the consideration of supramolecular constructs in other coordination compounds of lidocaine, including bis(lidocaine) tetrachloroferrate(III) chloride [29], bis(lidocaine) diaquatetrathiocyanatonicelate(II) [30] and bis(lidocaine) tetrathiocyanatocobaltate(II) monohydrate [31].

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